

Effects of Levothyroxine Therapy on Pregnancy and Neonatal Outcomes in Subclinical Hypothyroidism

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Abstract:

Background: Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) during pregnancy has been associated with adverse maternal and fetal outcomes. This study aimed to investigate the effects of levothyroxine (LT4) therapy on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in women with SCH.

Methods: A prospective, randomized controlled trial was conducted on 200 pregnant women with SCH, who were allocated to either the LT4 treatment group (n=100) or the control group (n=100). Thyroid function tests were monitored throughout pregnancy, and pregnancy and neonatal outcomes were assessed.

Results: The incidence of miscarriage (4% vs. 11%, p=0.06), preterm birth (7% vs. 15%, p=0.07), gestational hypertension (6% vs. 13%, p=0.09), and fetal growth restriction (5% vs. 12%, p=0.08) was lower in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group, although the differences were not statistically significant. The mean neonatal birth weight was significantly higher in the LT4 treatment group (3285 ± 458 g vs. 3142 ± 527 g, p=0.04). Thyroid function tests were significantly better in the LT4 treatment group throughout pregnancy (p<0.01).

Conclusion: LT4 treatment in pregnant women with SCH may have potential benefits in reducing adverse pregnancy outcomes and improving neonatal birth weight. Regular thyroid function screening and appropriate management of SCH during pregnancy are important for optimizing maternal and fetal outcomes.

Keywords: Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Pregnancy, Levothyroxine, Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes, Neonatal Outcomes.

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Introduction

Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is a common endocrine disorder characterized by elevated serum thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels with normal free thyroxine (FT4) concentrations [1]. The prevalence of SCH in pregnancy ranges from 2% to 5%, making it a significant concern for both maternal and fetal health [2]. Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in fetal neurodevelopment, particularly during the first trimester when the fetus relies entirely on maternal thyroid hormone supply [3]. Untreated SCH during pregnancy has been associated with various adverse outcomes, including miscarriage, preterm birth, gestational hypertension, and impaired cognitive development in offspring [4].

Levothyroxine (LT4) therapy is the standard treatment for overt hypothyroidism during pregnancy, aiming to maintain TSH levels within the trimester-specific reference range [5]. However, the management of SCH in pregnancy remains controversial due to conflicting evidence regarding the benefits of LT4 treatment on pregnancy and

neonatal outcomes [6]. Some studies have suggested that LT4 therapy may reduce the risk of miscarriage and preterm birth in women with SCH [7], while others have found no significant improvements in these outcomes [8].

The potential benefits of LT4 treatment in SCH during pregnancy extend beyond reducing the risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes. Adequate thyroid hormone levels are essential for optimal fetal brain development, and maternal hypothyroidism has been linked to impaired cognitive function in children [9]. A systematic review and meta-analysis by Maraka et al. found that LT4 therapy in pregnant women with SCH may improve neurocognitive outcomes in offspring, although the evidence was limited [10].

Despite the potential benefits of LT4 treatment in SCH during pregnancy, there are also concerns regarding the risks of overtreatment. Excessive LT4 dosage can lead to iatrogenic hyperthyroidism, which has been associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes such as gestational hypertension and low

birth weight [11]. Therefore, careful monitoring of thyroid function and appropriate dose adjustments are crucial throughout pregnancy to maintain euthyroidism and avoid the potential risks of overtreatment [12].

Given the high prevalence of SCH in pregnancy and its potential impact on maternal and fetal health, it is essential to evaluate the effects of LT4 therapy on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. This article aims to provide a comprehensive review of the current literature on the use of LT4 in pregnant women with SCH, examining its influence on various pregnancy complications, fetal growth, and neurodevelopmental outcomes in offspring. By synthesizing the available evidence, we hope to provide valuable insights into the management of SCH during pregnancy and guide clinical decision-making to optimize maternal and fetal health outcomes.

Aims and Objectives

This study aimed to investigate the effects of levothyroxine (LT4) therapy on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in women with subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH). The primary objective was to evaluate the impact of LT4 treatment on the incidence of adverse pregnancy outcomes, including miscarriage, preterm birth, gestational hypertension, and fetal growth restriction. The secondary objective was to assess the influence of LT4 therapy on neonatal outcomes, such as birth weight, Apgar scores, and neurodevelopmental milestones.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Participants: A prospective, randomized controlled trial was conducted from January 2023 to April 2024 at a tertiary care center. The study population consisted of pregnant women with SCH, defined as an elevated serum thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) level (2.5-10 mIU/L) with normal free thyroxine (FT4) concentrations (0.3-1.9 ng/dL & 0.6-1.6 ng/dl in 1st and 2nd trimester respectively). The inclusion criteria were singleton pregnancies, gestational age less than 20 weeks, and no prior history of thyroid disorders. Women with overt hypothyroidism, multiple pregnancies, chronic medical conditions, or those taking medications that could interfere with thyroid function were excluded from the study.

Sample Size and Randomization: A total of 200 pregnant women with SCH were enrolled in the study. The sample size was calculated based on a power of 80% and a significance level of 0.05, considering a 20% reduction in the incidence of adverse pregnancy outcomes with LT4 treatment. Participants were randomly allocated in a 1:1 ratio to either the LT4 treatment group or the control group using a computer-generated randomization

sequence. Block randomization with a block size of four was employed to ensure balanced group allocation.

Intervention and Follow-up: Women in the LT4 treatment group received levothyroxine at a starting dose of 1.20-1.42 µg/kg/day, which was adjusted based on TSH levels to maintain a target range of 0.1-2.5 mIU/L. The control group received no treatment but underwent regular monitoring of thyroid function. Participants were followed up monthly until delivery, and thyroid function tests (TSH and FT4) were performed at each visit. Prenatal care and delivery were managed according to standard obstetric guidelines.

Data Collection and Outcome Measures: Maternal demographic characteristics, medical history, and pregnancy-related information were collected at enrollment. The primary outcome measures included the incidence of miscarriage (pregnancy loss before 20 weeks), preterm birth (delivery before 37 weeks), gestational hypertension (blood pressure $\geq$ 140/90 mmHg after 20 weeks), and fetal growth restriction (estimated fetal weight <10th percentile). Secondary outcomes included neonatal birth weight, Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, and neurodevelopmental milestones assessed using the Bayley Scales of Infant Development III at 6 months of age.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the baseline characteristics of the study population. Continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation or median (interquartile range), while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The primary and secondary outcomes were compared between the LT4 treatment and control groups using independent t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. Logistic regression analysis was performed to adjust for potential confounders. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS software version 24.0.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. The trial was registered in the Clinical Trials Registry. Participant confidentiality was maintained throughout the study, and data were anonymized for analysis and reporting purposes.

Results

Baseline Characteristics: A total of 200 pregnant women with subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) were enrolled in the study and randomly allocated to either the levothyroxine (LT4) treatment group (n=100) or the control group (n=100). The baseline characteristics of the study population were similar

between the two groups (Table 1). The mean maternal age was 28.5 ± 4.7 years in the LT4 treatment group and 29.1 ± 5.2 years in the control group ($p=0.39$). The mean gestational age at enrollment was 12.3 ± 2.1 weeks and 12.7 ± 2.3 weeks in the LT4 treatment and control groups, respectively ($p=0.20$). The median TSH levels at enrollment were 4.2 mIU/L (interquartile range [IQR]: 3.1-5.8) in the LT4 treatment group and 4.4 mIU/L (IQR: 3.2-6.1) in the control group ($p=0.42$). The mean FT4 levels at enrollment were similar between the groups (1.2 ± 0.3 ng/dL vs. 1.1 ± 0.2 ng/dL, $p=0.31$).

Primary Outcomes: The incidence of adverse pregnancy outcomes was lower in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group, although the differences did not reach statistical significance (Table 2). The miscarriage rate was 4% in the LT4 treatment group and 11% in the control group (odds ratio [OR]: 0.34, 95% confidence interval [CI]: 0.10-1.09, $p=0.06$). Preterm birth occurred in 7% of women in the LT4 treatment group and 15% in the control group (OR: 0.43, 95% CI: 0.17-1.10, $p=0.07$). Gestational hypertension was observed in 6% of the LT4 treatment group and 13% of the control group (OR: 0.43, 95% CI: 0.15-1.18, $p=0.09$). Fetal growth restriction was present in 5% of the LT4 treatment group and 12% of the control group (OR: 0.38, 95% CI: 0.13-1.13, $p=0.08$).

Secondary Outcomes: The mean neonatal birth weight was significantly higher in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group (3285 ± 458 g vs. 3142 ± 527 g, $p=0.04$) (Table 3). The median Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes were similar between the groups ($p=0.62$ and $p=0.85$, respectively). The mean neurodevelopmental milestones scores at 6 months were 97.2 ± 10.5 in the LT4 treatment group and 94.6 ± 12.1 in the control group ($p=0.10$).

Thyroid Function Tests: Thyroid function tests were monitored throughout pregnancy in both groups (Table 4). The median TSH levels were significantly lower in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group at all time points from 13-16 weeks of gestation onward ($p<0.01$). The mean FT4 levels were significantly higher in

the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group from 13-16 weeks of gestation until the end of pregnancy ($p<0.01$).

Subgroup Analysis: A subgroup analysis of primary outcomes based on TSH levels at enrollment was performed (Table 5). In the TSH stratum of 2.5-4.0 mIU/L, the odds ratios for miscarriage, preterm birth, gestational hypertension, and fetal growth restriction were 0.45 (95% CI: 0.08-2.58, $p=0.36$), 0.43 (95% CI: 0.10-1.84, $p=0.25$), 0.35 (95% CI: 0.06-1.91, $p=0.21$), and 0.45 (95% CI: 0.08-2.58, $p=0.36$), respectively. Similar trends were observed in the TSH strata of 4.1-6.0 mIU/L and >6.0 mIU/L, although the differences were not statistically significant.

Adverse Events: The incidence of adverse events and side effects was similar between the LT4 treatment and control groups (Table 6). Headache was reported in 8% of the LT4 treatment group and 5% of the control group ($p=0.39$). Palpitations occurred in 6% of the LT4 treatment group and 3% of the control group ($p=0.31$). Insomnia was reported in 5% of the LT4 treatment group and 4% of the control group ($p=0.73$).

Logistic Regression Analysis: A logistic regression analysis was performed to adjust for potential confounders (Table 7). After adjusting for maternal age, BMI, parity, and baseline TSH levels, the odds ratios for miscarriage, preterm birth, gestational hypertension, and fetal growth restriction in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group were 0.31 (95% CI: 0.09-1.05, $p=0.06$), 0.40 (95% CI: 0.15-1.08, $p=0.07$), 0.41 (95% CI: 0.14-1.17, $p=0.09$), and 0.36 (95% CI: 0.12-1.11, $p=0.08$), respectively.

In summary, this study found that LT4 treatment in pregnant women with SCH was associated with a trend towards reduced rates of adverse pregnancy outcomes, although the differences did not reach statistical significance. LT4 treatment significantly improved thyroid function throughout pregnancy and resulted in a higher mean neonatal birth weight. The incidence of adverse events was similar between the groups. These findings suggest that LT4 treatment may have potential benefits in pregnant women with SCH, but larger studies are needed to confirm these results.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study population

Characteristic	LT4 Treatment Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Maternal age (years)	28.5 ± 4.7	29.1 ± 5.2	0.39
Gestational age at enrollment (weeks)	12.3 ± 2.1	12.7 ± 2.3	0.20
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	24.6 ± 3.9	25.1 ± 4.2	0.38
Parity (nulliparous/multiparous)	58/42	62/38	0.56
TSH levels at enrollment (mIU/L)	4.2 (3.1-5.8)	4.4 (3.2-6.1)	0.42
FT4 levels at enrollment (ng/dL)	1.2 ± 0.3	1.1 ± 0.2	0.31

Table 2: Primary outcomes in the LT4 treatment and control groups

Outcome	LT4 Treatment Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Miscarriage	4 (4%)	11 (11%)	0.34 (0.10-1.09)	0.06
Preterm birth	7 (7%)	15 (15%)	0.43 (0.17-1.10)	0.07
Gestational hypertension	6 (6%)	13 (13%)	0.43 (0.15-1.18)	0.09
Fetal growth restriction	5 (5%)	12 (12%)	0.38 (0.13-1.13)	0.08

Table 3: Secondary outcomes in the LT4 treatment and control groups

Outcome	LT4 Treatment Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Neonatal birth weight (g)	3285 ± 458	3142 ± 527	0.04
Apgar scores at 1 minute (median, IQR)	8 (7-9)	8 (7-9)	0.62
Apgar scores at 5 minutes (median, IQR)	9 (8-9)	9 (8-9)	0.85
Neurodevelopmental milestones at 6 months	97.2 ± 10.5	94.6 ± 12.1	0.10

Table 4: Thyroid function tests throughout pregnancy in the LT4 treatment and control groups

Gestational Age (weeks)	TSH (mIU/L)	FT4 (ng/dL)	p-value (TSH)	p-value (FT4)
13-16	2.5 / 4.6	1.3 / 1.1	<0.01	<0.01
17-20	1.9 / 4.8	1.4 / 1.0	<0.001	<0.001
21-24	1.7 / 5.1	1.4 / 1.0	<0.001	<0.001
25-28	1.6 / 5.3	1.5 / 0.9	<0.001	<0.001
29-32	1.8 / 5.5	1.4 / 0.9	<0.001	<0.001
33-36	2.1 / 5.6	1.3 / 0.8	<0.001	<0.001
37-40	2.4 / 5.8	1.2 / 0.8	<0.001	<0.001

Table 5: Subgroup analysis of primary outcomes based on TSH levels at enrollment

TSH Level (mIU/L)	Outcome	LT4 Treatment Group	Control Group	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
2.5-4.0	Miscarriage	2/48 (4.2%)	4/45(8.9%)	0.45 (0.08-2.58)	0.36
	Preterm birth	3/48 (6.3%)	6/45(13.3%)	0.43 (0.10-1.84)	0.25
	Gestational hypertension	2/48 (4.2%)	5/45(11.1%)	0.35 (0.06-1.91)	0.21
	Fetal growth restriction	2/48 (4.2%)	4/45(8.9%)	0.45 (0.08-2.58)	0.36
4.1-6.0	Miscarriage	1/35 (2.9%)	4/38(10.5%)	0.25 (0.03-2.33)	0.20
	Preterm birth	2/35 (5.7%)	6/38(15.8%)	0.32 (0.06-1.71)	0.17
	Gestational hypertension	2/35 (5.7%)	5/38(13.2%)	0.40 (0.07-2.18)	0.28
	Fetal growth restriction	2/35 (5.7%)	5/38(13.2%)	0.40 (0.07-2.18)	0.28
>6.0	Miscarriage	1/17 (5.9%)	3/17(17.6%)	0.29 (0.03-3.12)	0.30
	Preterm birth	2/17 (11.8%)	3/17 (17.6%)	0.62 (0.09-4.33)	0.63
	Gestational hypertension	2/17 (11.8%)	3/17 (17.6%)	0.62 (0.09-4.33)	0.63
	Fetal growth restriction	1/17 (5.9%)	3/17 (17.6%)	0.29 (0.03-3.12)	0.30

Table 6: Adverse events and side effects in the LT4 treatment and control groups

Adverse Event	LT4 Treatment Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)	p-value
Headache	8 (8%)	5 (5%)	0.39
Palpitations	6 (6%)	3 (3%)	0.31
Insomnia	5 (5%)	4 (4%)	0.73

Table 7: Logistic regression analysis for primary outcomes

Outcome	Adjusted Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Miscarriage	0.31 (0.09-1.05)	0.06
Preterm birth	0.40 (0.15-1.08)	0.07
Gestational hypertension	0.41 (0.14-1.17)	0.09
Fetal growth restriction	0.36 (0.12-1.11)	0.08

Covariates included in the logistic regression model: maternal age, BMI, parity, and baseline TSH levels.

Discussion

The present study investigated the effects of levothyroxine (LT4) therapy on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in women with subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH). The findings suggest that LT4 treatment may have potential benefits in reducing adverse pregnancy outcomes, although the differences did not reach statistical significance.

The incidence of miscarriage in the LT4 treatment group was lower compared to the control group (4% vs. 11%, $p=0.06$). This finding is consistent with a previous study by Maraka et al., which reported a significantly lower risk of pregnancy loss in women with SCH treated with LT4 (adjusted odds ratio [aOR]: 0.62, 95% CI: 0.48-0.82) [11]. However, a randomized controlled trial by Casey et al. found no significant difference in the rate of pregnancy loss between the LT4 treatment and placebo groups (4.6% vs. 3.2%, $p=0.87$) [12].

Preterm birth occurred in 7% of the LT4 treatment group and 15% of the control group ($p=0.07$) in the current study. A meta-analysis by Nazarpour et al. reported a significantly lower risk of preterm delivery in women with SCH treated with LT4 (relative risk [RR]: 0.41, 95% CI: 0.24-0.68) [13]. In contrast, a study by Ju et al. found no significant difference in the rate of preterm birth between the LT4 treatment and control groups (5.1% vs. 7.8%, $p=0.38$) [14].

The incidence of gestational hypertension was lower in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group (6% vs. 13%, $p=0.09$). This finding is in line with a study by Nazarpour et al., which reported a significantly lower risk of gestational hypertension in women with SCH treated with LT4 (RR: 0.35, 95% CI: 0.13-0.96) [15]. However, a study by Zhao et al. found no significant difference in the incidence of gestational hypertension between the LT4 treatment and control groups (3.3% vs. 5.6%, $p=0.36$) [16].

Fetal growth restriction was observed in 5% of the LT4 treatment group and 12% of the control group ($p=0.08$) in the present study. A study by Zhu et al. reported a significantly lower risk of fetal growth restriction in women with SCH treated with LT4 (aOR: 0.31, 95% CI: 0.11-0.87) [17]. However, a study by Maraka et al. found no significant difference in the incidence of small for gestational age between the LT4 treatment and control groups (8.1% vs. 8.5%, $p=0.76$) [11].

The mean neonatal birth weight was significantly higher in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group (3285 ± 458 g vs. 3142 ± 527 g,

$p=0.04$). This finding is consistent with a study by Nazarpour et al., which reported a significantly higher mean birth weight in the LT4 treatment group compared to the control group (3229 ± 458 g vs. 3076 ± 479 g, $p=0.02$) [15]. However, a study by Casey et al. found no significant difference in the mean birth weight between the LT4 treatment and placebo groups (3345 ± 551 g vs. 3358 ± 537 g, $p=0.80$) [12].

The strengths of the present study include the prospective, randomized controlled design, the use of a standardized protocol for LT4 treatment, and the regular monitoring of thyroid function throughout pregnancy. However, the study also has several limitations. The sample size may have been insufficient to detect significant differences in some outcomes, and the follow-up period was limited to 6 months after delivery. Additionally, the study was conducted at a single center, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.

This study suggests that LT4 treatment in pregnant women with SCH may have potential benefits in reducing adverse pregnancy outcomes, although larger studies are needed to confirm these results. The findings highlight the importance of regular thyroid function screening and appropriate management of SCH during pregnancy to optimize maternal and fetal outcomes. Future research should focus on identifying the optimal timing and dosage of LT4 treatment, as well as the long-term effects on child development.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this prospective, randomized controlled study investigated the effects of levothyroxine (LT4) therapy on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in women with subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH). The findings suggest that LT4 treatment may have potential benefits in reducing adverse pregnancy outcomes, such as miscarriage, preterm birth, gestational hypertension, and fetal growth restriction, although the differences did not reach statistical significance. LT4 treatment significantly improved thyroid function throughout pregnancy and resulted in a higher mean neonatal birth weight compared to the control group.

The results of this study add to the growing body of evidence supporting the importance of regular thyroid function screening and appropriate management of SCH during pregnancy. By maintaining euthyroidism throughout gestation, LT4 treatment may help optimize maternal and fetal outcomes, reducing the risk of complications and ensuring healthy fetal development.

However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study, including the relatively small sample size and the single-center design.

Larger, multi-center randomized controlled trials are needed to confirm these findings and provide more robust evidence for the benefits of LT4 treatment in pregnant women with SCH.

Future research should focus on identifying the optimal timing and dosage of LT4 treatment, as well as the long-term effects on child development. Additionally, cost-effectiveness analyses should be conducted to evaluate the economic impact of implementing universal thyroid function screening and LT4 treatment for pregnant women with SCH.

In summary, this study highlights the potential benefits of LT4 therapy in pregnant women with SCH and underscores the importance of regular thyroid function monitoring and appropriate management during pregnancy. Healthcare providers should be aware of the potential risks associated with SCH in pregnancy and consider implementing screening and treatment strategies to improve maternal and fetal outcomes.

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